

REPRESENTATION OF CHILD SEXUAL ABUSE IN PAKISTANI NEWS MEDIA: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study explores "Representation of Child Sexual Abuse in Pakistani News Media: A Critical Discourse Analysis of a Case Study". This study has followed a mixed method research design by implementing critical discourse analysis within the socio-cognitive framework developed by Van Dijk (1984). So, the objectives of this study are to explore the use of language and discourse that shape public perception of CSA in Pakistani news media. Secondly, Appraise the impact of the discourse among the readership by exploring various perspectives using a critical discourse analysis. And Analyse the truth behind the print media outlets (newspapers) to understand journalist's ideologies concerning the representation of CSA in newspaper. The findings divulge concerning aspects of media coverage, including the manipulation of emotions to attract attention, the prioritisation of statements from the authoritative figures in lieu of comprehensive coverage, and the influence of societal taboos, cultural norms, and the media's agenda. The importance of a responsible journalist is that treats child sexual abuse as a serious issue which is emphasized and discouraging its exploitation for profit or political gain. The implications of this study extend to media students, educators, politicians, and researchers, contributing to the social responsibility of the news media to address CSA. This study offers significant knowledge on how CSA is reported in Pakistani news media and emphasises the need for sensitive reporting that puts the needs of victims first and spreads awareness rather than serving one's political or personal agendas. This study provides a minor but crucial step toward nourishing the ethical and social responsibility of journalism that addresses the serious issue of CSA by examining media coverage. Besides, it would be helpful to concentrate critical insights to the readers.

Keywords: Child Sexual Abuse, Sensationalism, Societal taboos, Social Responsibility, Journalism, Pakistani News Media, Critical Discourse Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) is a heinous crime that penetrates geographical boundaries and affects societies worldwide. According to the American Psychological Association (1999), CSA shows sexual purposes during the interaction between a kid and an adult or another person who is much older than the

child or in a position of authority or influence over the child (Nair, 2019). Likewise, CSA is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as "The involvement of a child in sexual activity that they do not fully understand, cannot provide informed consent for, are not developmentally prepared for, or

that takes place in violation of legal or societal norms" (Lemaigre, P. Taylor & Gittoes, 2017). Additionally, other types of acts, such as masturbating in front of the minor, sending inappropriate text messages online, blackmailing, and flirting are also included in the category of child sexual abuse.

The effects of child sexual abuse on the victims are severe and long-lasting, sexual violence causes significant physical, psychological, and societal trauma. Injuries, illnesses, unintended pregnancies, social isolation, and psychological distress are all more common for victims, as are elevated risks of HIV and other sexually transmitted infections (Dendevnorov, 2022) and to deal with their pain, some victims turn to dangerous practices like the consumption of drugs (Peña, 2023). Furthermore, as child victims reach adulthood, sexual abuse can impair practices to take care of both them and others (UNICEF, 2022). Therefore, examining how CSA is portrayed in the media; essential to address the significant issue since the media knowingly influences public views, policy debates, and societal change.

CSA is one of the biggest problems in industrialised countries around the world, it is a complex and burning issue, and countries like Pakistan and India are the most affected countries in the world. As per Statistics, Pakistan is one of the countries where 12 or more children are molested in a single day. Moreover, out of the total incidents of CSA that were documented, 2,325 victims were girls (55%), and 1,928 victims were boys (45%). Most of the perpetrators were acquaintances of the victims. Children between the ages of 6 and 15 are the most vulnerable and easy targets – "Sahil, Cruel Numbers 2022" (Murtaza & Manj, 2022).

The cultural and social fabric of Pakistani society play a significant role in perpetuating silence and taboos surrounding. As survivor support CSA Officer Sheeraz Ahmed, who is affiliated with the Karachi-based NGO War Against Rape, aptly describes, "If we look at Pakistani society, it is a conservative society, and rape is considered taboo there. People don't talk about it; they victimize themselves." Overcoming these societal barriers and raising awareness about the CSA requires proactive efforts from various stakeholders, including the

media.

The purpose of this study is to look at how CSA is portrayed in Pakistani news media. This study evaluates whether the media prioritises the pursuit of justice above sensationalising situations to gain attention and sheds insight into how the media portrays cases of CSA. This study aims to advance knowledge of the media's obligation to address this pressing issue by analysing how CSA is represented in the media. In the end, the study's primary goal is to investigate and analyse the reporting of CSA occurrences in Pakistani news media, providing knowledge that can guide future interventions and policy actions.

So, the objectives of this study are to:

- Analyse the truth behind the print media outlets (newspapers) to understand journalist's ideologies concerning the representation of CSA in newspaper.
 - Asses the way of sensationalism of the CSA's cases among reputable newspapers Pakistan The Dawn and The Express tribune in the context of CSA.
 - Appraise the impact of the discourse among the readership by exploring various perspectives using a critical discourse analysis.
- And the research questions for this study are:
- What role do authoritative figures, such as politicians and religious leaders, play in shaping media coverage of CSA?
 - To what extent do Pakistani newspapers, such as Dawn and The Express Tribune, over-sensationalize CSA cases to attract readership?
 - How does the use of language and discourse shape public perception of CSA in Pakistani news media?

Literature Review

CSA is the most vulnerable and delicate issue across the globe. According to the Report by the Regional Director of the World Health Organization (2004), CSA is "the involvement of a child in sexual behaviours that he or she does not completely comprehend, is unable to provide proper consent to, is not old enough to understand, for which the child is not developmentally prepared, or elsewhere that violates the laws or social taboos of society" (WHO, 2020). Even CSA occurs in Pakistan, but it is still considered as a taboo. For instance,

Pakistani society allows sex conversation generally, but discussing CSA is regarded as immoral (Avais et al., 2020). This cultural reluctance to address CSA complicates efforts to openly confront and address the critical issue.

In a similar vein, the American Psychological Association (1999) states that psychologically it is a contact between a child and an adult or another person who is either considerably older than the child or who has authority over the child. Although there have been many changes in the socio-political discourse on child abuse throughout the years although the fundamental understanding remains constant. Child abuse is mostly defined by society in terms of how it is viewed as criminal conduct and how the law defines the offence. When it involves a child, sexual misconduct is typically viewed as an action that blurs the line between immorality and criminality (Kitzinger, 2004).

Analysing media coverage of CSA, it was observed that the role of media is crucial in transforming the problem of CSA into an important social issue by linking it to other social pathologies like domestic violence, family conflicts, separation of parents, re-settlement, and so on (Collings 2002; Nair 2019). Undoubtedly, the media may make the problem obvious and significant by covering distant cases of abuse and putting them on the political and public agenda. It can simplify the CSA social construct, supporting local efforts to increase awareness of the problem and inform the public about strategies for preventing it (Courtney, 1999).

Whereas the national and local media typically ignore many criteria, including ethics and legal requirements observed, facts, presentation, terminology, objectivity, relevant information, and follow-up (Finkelhor, 1994). Furthermore, examining how child abuse is portrayed in Australian and New Zealand tabloid media, Wilczynski and Sinclair (1999) observed that the media can be a great resource for social advocates by putting the issue in the proper perspective through news articles, guest columns, editorials, and reports. A thorough media investigation into the CSA can put pressure on government agencies to implement stringent prevention measures.

Nair (2019) elucidates that sensitive information, including the child's and family's identities, was unnecessarily publicised or shared on social media in some child abuse cases reported from India to sensationalise the tale. Such reporting deteriorates the social stigma of shame or secondary victimisation of the non-offending family members, failing to portray the crime in the proper light (Cote and Bucqueroux, 1996), which also becomes one of the justifications for not reporting abuse cases; only a few Pakistani print media have published the names of sex crime victims (Tahir, 2021). Making such a mistake, and no one has thought about it or exerted considerable control over the media since the media tended to advocate for illegal freedoms, which opened the door for public manipulation and allowed doubt of the media's credibility.

Subsequently, journalists may accomplish much more without taking sides. They can examine the treatment of victims in various situations as well as the different types of trauma they experience over the course of the judicial and investigative processes (Nair, 2019). Additionally, it was noted that the media frequently focuses exclusively on bringing attention to the victim rather than discussing preventative measures and ways to keep children safe both inside and outside (Collings, 2002).

Maydell (2018) briefly describes that the news media primarily used serialised criminal tales with overly sensationalised content to frame the issue of child abuse, highlighting the scary episodes with aggressive types of abuse more than the other types of aggressiveness. It is an accurate to say that the media has not looked at conditions critically or reported on less significant criminal cases appropriately. Berkeley Media Studies and Frameworks Institute (2011) explicates that the criminal justice perspective dominates media coverage of child sexual abuse (CSA), which tends to ignore the socio-ethical components of abuse (Nair, 2019).

Indeed, child abuse issues are frequently covered by the media as criminal stories meant to grab people's attention and frequently represent stereotypical views of society without any critical examination of the problem (Mejia

et al., 2012). The complexities of phrases like sexual abuse, sexual assault, molestation, and inappropriate behaviour are frequently difficult for reporters to properly understand. Being upfront regarding how child abuse cases should be reported in the media crucially, as it will help journalists reporting the incidents understand how and to what extent the case needs to be covered and publicised (Burrows, 1988).

Apart from only concentrating on case studies, the media should play an essential role in drawing attention to the sensitive aspect of the subject of child sexual abuse by employing solution-oriented strategies (Kitzinger & Skidmore, 1995).

As stated by Aristotle, "the orator must install an attitude inclined toward obeying the rule of law." In simple terms, the speaker's (author's) fundamental objective is to persuade the audience to accept an opinion that is favourable to him or her. The speaker (or author) strategically employs appeals to logic (logos), evoking audience emotions (pathos), and establishing personal character (ethos) to specifically influence an audience in distinct manners. In Aristotelian rhetoric, ethos, derived from the Greek term "character," underscores the credibility and authority granted to the writer or speaker, or those called upon to support an argument. The objective of this appeal is to instil trust among the audience and to ensure the reliability and credibility of the author (Teneva, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

Social Responsibility

The social responsibility theory expounds that the media must report all relevant information and need to be sufficiently skilled to ensure that their work effectively serves the public; therefore, they would pledge dedication to several practices (Davis, 1986). The fundamental principle of this idea is that there are local media sources that are both publicly and privately owned and that the main goal of all media is to serve society rather than to make a profit.

Moreover, McQuail (1987) postulates that the social responsibility theory is normative; it explains how the media ought to ideally operate under a structure of social norms. In

the media, which is viewed as an outlet for the voiceless to be heard and for fostering the development of public opinion, everyone has the right to speak, express themselves, and publish. It is viewed as a tool for social advancement rather than a goal in and of itself. The stated objectives of media include informing, documenting, analysing, interpreting, mediating, mobilising, finding and developing solutions. On the other hand, the authority fallacy is also prominent to expose the authors' modern manipulation techniques.

Appeal to an Authorities Fallacy

There are tactics used to persuade an audience by mentioning authority falsely in the text where the higher authority has used the power to sensationalise or exaggerate the case rather than doing their job, which is professionalism. Thus, the understanding drawn from empirical studies is that this fallacy is created by showing an authoritative figure that does not only highlight the case but also set political agendas and drive the public to make someone dominant. Therefore, the core reason behind the tabloidization of news will be predicted as profit-generating and persuading the public to form an opinion by sensationalising crime stories rather than educating the victim's family to heal and get medical and other social or psychological assistance concerning to CSA. For instance, they provide others' opinions as facts that have not been verified by scientists. They implemented such facts to support their claims. "Contemporary online news readers are more inclined to trust opinion leaders, influencers, bloggers, and perceived experts or authorities over verified fact." (Teneva, 2023). This illustrates that they follow their leader or authoritative figure rather than investigating imperial answers themselves. Whatever they produce, it will be mentioned just as an institution's name, but they take the case personally. This means a higher figure of authority is used to make newsworthy statements and gain public attention.

Dawn (Oct. 25, 2022) likewise "Police told the journalist, and the mother or the victim told the police, etc." Furthermore, media outlets use prominent institutional names to support their claims. However, this is an implicit opinion of the author, which may be considered biased

and driven by certain conditions that violate ethics. This type of rhetoric is used to support political agendas, but it is an unfair representation of the vulnerable issue of child sexual abuse. In a similar view, appeals of pseudo-(false) authority are being used as manipulation tools. Further, it has three subcategories that also expound on the false emerging tactics of modern authors, which may conceal “self-interest”, “biases”, “political agenda setting” and “misrepresentation of the news” by using plethora statistics to affirm negative claims, celebrity or authority use for emphasis on purposeful agenda setting, and self-generated sources to gain an implicit objective.

Appeals to Pseudo-Authority or False Authorities

Pseudo-authority, as defined by Teneva (2023), refers to individuals or entities presented as credible sources of information despite lacking genuine expertise or relevance to the topic at hand. This misrepresentation of authority typically manifests through **quotations, testimonials, and celebrity endorsements**, aiming to exploit our inherent trust in figures of perceived knowledge and influence audience behaviour. On the other hand, those manipulation techniques would also impact the communities of those who are unable to comprehend such modern tactics and increase the likelihood of mass isolation and anxiety. Furthermore, the three subcategories will enhance the critical vision of the learner.

Appeals to “Nominal” Pseudo-Authorities or False Expert

The role modal or sensational person is used to spread information and make someone’s opinion about any topic where the audience feels that this opinion is their personal but actually that is controlled by the new tactics of the modern media, i.e., the media shows any famous personality to gain attention towards a particular case i.e. “Murad Ali Shah suggested police a way to CCTV footage and Sharjeel Inam Memon tweeted that our government has caught the predator through the CCTV footage and Police IG was also presented over there” (Dawn 25 Oct, 2022; Express Tribune 27 Oct, 2022). Additionally various irrelevant

authorities were used to sensationalise the case. This sort of tactic is highlighted in news media. It does not make any sense to make the prevalent mentioning of these sorts of things in CSA case representation. Dichotomously, this might be considered by someone as a political marketing of the serving government owing to showing CSA as a product. Subsequently, this is how you do not have your opinion about CSA, and this would be driven opinion by the media’s modern orator.

Appeal to “Implicit” Pseudo-Authorities

Refers to rhetorical strategies of journalists in which orator create sources by themselves or when there is no sign of indication about information and knowledge to transmit information deliberately and journalists feel specific evidence does not require to the audience and public believe easily. Therefore, they use such tactics.

For example, they may conclude that “Police said”. But there is a whole department which one has said them. The journalists do not specify in their reports Secondly, they may say there is an “expert opinion, observer or famous politician’s view” may be cited to form a position but they will never mention who is an expert and who is a famous personality retrieved from (Down 2022; Express Tribune 2022). The rhetoric perceives themselves and write what they want. This sort of thing would be regarded as implicit pseudo-authorities if the writers do not mention authentic sources of information. Hence, this is how the rhetoric’s do have to justify the information or knowledge he/she has mentioned in the report about CSA. But journalist mention what they want to make the feel audience.

Appeals to “Pseudo-Visibility”

Teneva (2023) defines the concept of pseudo-visibility as the excessive or misleading use of data and statistics to create a misleading impression of objectivity and transparency. This phenomenon is prevalent in fields such as news, advertising, and politics, leveraging our reliance on the digital data to facilitate us achieve specific goals. This is often accomplished by ignoring context, obscuring nuance, and limiting different interpretations. As Best (2001) warns, navigating these

“damning lies and statistics” requires watchfulness and critical evaluation of the information propagated in the media and elsewhere. Whether encountering overestimated axes in charts. Further, the following example illustrates the complete picture of pseudo visibility.

For example, “According to statistics, more than 12 children are estimated to be abused daily in Pakistan. Among the reported cases of child abuse, 55% (2,325) of the victims were girls, while 45% (1,928) were boys.” retrieved (Express Tribune, 2022). They have mentioned that 93% per cent of perpetrators of child sexual abuse are relatives or acquaintances and the other 7% per cent are strangers or they will mention that 45% per cent are boys and 55% per cent of the victims of child sexual abuse are girls. After revealing such data author may put his/her agenda or also navigate with statistics to support negative claims to influence the audience. Similarly, as observed from the news article, news media manipulate audiences by using many accurate data to support their political agenda. In turn, laymen will understand all the data without his /her interpretations that may make him/her think and decide to agree with the implicit agendas of authors rather than going further to think and critically evaluate the sensitive issue of CSA.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is a set of logical steps used to collect and examine data to get a deeper knowledge of an issue or subject (Akinyode & Khan, 2018). In this study, both qualitative and quantitative research approach is used to capture the complexities of the research phenomenon, specifically a case study research design is selected as it provides an opportunity to learn concrete, contextual, in-depth knowledge about a specific real-world subject. Further, the socio-cognitive technique developed by Van Dijk is used to conduct a critical discourse analysis of the chosen reports.

SOCIO-COGNITIVE MODEL (CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS)

Socio-Cognitive Discourse Analysis is a framework of the study that explores the relationship between cognition, discourse, and

society. It has evolved to incorporate elements of the psychological model to understand discursive practices of memory and concept of cognitive science. Van Dijk's extensive research focuses on various topics, including stereotypes, the perpetuation of ethnic prejudice, the misuse of power by elites, and the resistance exhibited by marginalised groups. Van Dijk (1998) defined CDA as “a field dedicated to analyzing spoken and written texts to uncover the discursive roots of power, dominance, inequality, and bias” (Bukhari & Xiaoyang, 2013). It investigates at the maintenance and reproducibility of these discursive sources within certain social, political, and historical settings (Derveni and Tsitsanoudis-Mallidis, 2018).

SAMPLING AND DATA ANALYSIS

The data for this study is sourced from reported news on selected case of child sexual abuse published in Pakistan's two prominent newspapers - Dawn and The Express Tribune. For data collection, non-probability purposive sampling was used, and news articles published between October 25, 2022, and October 29, 2022, were selected for analysis. These articles are analysed using the socio-cognitive paradigm of critical discourse analysis developed by Dijk (1998). The analysis focuses on identifying patterns, themes, and discursive strategies that pertained to power, dominance, inequality, and bias in the portrayal of child sexual abuse. This study also used Linguistic Inquiry Word Count (LIWC) software to examine the linguistic aspects of newspapers, likewise, the frequency of specific words and categories, including positive and negative tones, cognitive processes, and social dimensions. Additionally, the research team conducted independent analyses of the selected news articles, and regular discussions were held via video calling and in-person meetings to establish reliability and reduce subjective biases.

"The main characteristics of the target population that qualify sample to participate in a study" are what Hulley et al. (2013) define as inclusion criteria. These standards assist in ensuring the accuracy of the study sample and the results apply to the population under investigation. According to Creswell (2014), exclusion criteria help minimise variables

contributing to bias or variation in the study's findings.

Inclusion Criteria Description	Exclusion Criteria Description
Sample size; minimum 5 times consecutive publication of the case on newspaper. e.g., The Dawn and The Express Tribune.	Less than 5 publisher's newspaper were excluded. e.g., The News, The Nation etc.
Those included which publish on the topic CSA and other related social and cultural issues.	Other publisher like, Business Recorder and Economy related are not relevant.
Only English publisher Newspaper.	Urdu and Sindhi publisher such as Daily Jang, Daily Aaj and Kawish, and Sindh Times etc.
News articles published between October 25, 2022, and October 29, 2022	Afterwards the specified date.

To obtain the information required for analysis, data-collecting strategies are methodically used (Creswell, 2014). Both

quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques have been utilized in this study.

Methods	Descriptions
Qualitative	Critical Discourse Analysis by using Socio cognitive model of Van Dijk.
Quantitative	Machine Learning model known as Linguistic Inquiry Word Count (LIWC)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The LIWC refers to linguistic inquiry word count in which traditional dimensions are used in dictionaries to identify the word either it is positive or negative, and cognitive etc. By gauging their percentage by using machine

learning where numbers of word have been categorized by machine as a positive or negative with their meaning prescribed in entries or dictionaries with help of numerous years of study.

LIWC at Dawn

Traditional LIWC Dimension	Your Text	Average for Formal Language
-words (I, me, my)	0.06	0.67
Positive Tone	1.16	2.33
Negative Tone	1.88	1.38
Social Words	11.23	6.54
Cognitive Processes	5.5	7.95
Allure	2.7	3.58
Moralization	0.99	0.30
Summary Variables		
Analytic	98.09	87.63
Authentic	11.39	28.90

Results from the LIWC analysis of Dawn articles reveal intriguing patterns in linguistic features. The I-words (I, me, my) are used at a rate of 0.06 percent, which is lower than the average rate of formal language at 0.67 percent. The positive tone percentage is found at 1.16 percent, which is less than the average formal

language percentage of 2.33 percent. Conversely, the negative tone percentage is found at 1.88 percent, greater than the average formal language percentage of 1.38 percent. Furthermore, the text contains a higher percentage of social words, specifically 11.23 percent, compared to the average formal

language which has a percentage of 6.54 percent. While, cognitive processes are found at 5.5 percent, which is less than formal language's percentage of 7.95 percent. Delving deeper into specific dimensions, the allure (powerfully and mysteriously. attractive or fascinating; seductive) is identified at 2.7%, following behind the formal language standard of 3.58%. Contrarily, moralization is more prevalent in Dawn articles, accounting for 0.99%, exceeding the formal language average of 0.30%.

The summary of variables is based upon two dimensions. Firstly, an analytical dimension is measured to be 98.9 percent, which is higher than the average percentage of formal language, which is 87.63 percent. Secondly, an authentic dimension is measured at 11.39 percent, which is lower than the average percentage of formal language, which is 28.90 percent. From investigations, it has been interpreted that Dawn's writings have a high percentage of analytics and a low rate of Authenticity.

LIWC at The Express Tribune

Traditional LIWC Dimension	Your Text	Average for Formal Language
I-words (I, me, my)	0.00	0.67
Positive Tone	0.30	2.33
Negative Tone	3.77	1.38
Social Words	10.15	6.54
Cognitive Processes	5.45	7.95
Allure	2.35	3.58
Moralization	1.95	0.30
Summary Variables		
Analytic	96.73	87.63
Authentic	15.91	28.90

Employing the linguistic word count inquiry, our analysis of The Express Tribune articles reveals typical linguistic patterns categorized through the LIWC framework. Notably, the use of self-referential pronouns (I, me, my) is virtually absent, registering at 0.00%, a stark contrast to the average for formal language at 0.67%. The expression of a positive tone is limited to 0.30%, considerably below the formal language average of 2.33%, while the use of negative tone stands at 3.77%, surpassing the formal language average of 1.38%. Furthermore, social words are prevalent in The Express Tribune articles, constituting 10.15%, surpassing the average for formal language at 6.54%. However, cognitive processes are employed less frequently, representing 5.45%, compared to the formal

language average of 7.95%. Similarly, allure is noted at 2.35%, falling short of the formal language average of 3.58%, while moralization is pronounced at 1.95%, exceeding the formal language standard of 0.30%.

In summary, the analysis of summary variables highlights a dominant Analytic measurement in The Express Tribune articles, standing at 96.73%, significantly higher than the average for formal language at 87.63%. Conversely, authentic language use is observed at 15.91%, notably lower than the formal language average of 28.90%. This inquiry suggests that The Express Tribune's narratives, like Dawn's, have a significant amount of analytical content, resulting in a decrease in authenticity.

Comparison of LIWC

Traditional LIWC Dimension	Dawn	The Express Tribune	Avg. for Formal Language
I-words (I, me, my)	0.06	0	0.67
Positive Tone	1.16	0.3	2.33
Negative Tone	1.88	3.77	1.38
ocial Words	11.23	10.15	6.54
Cognitive Processes	5.5	5.45	7.95
Allure	2.7	2.35	3.58
Moralization	0.99	1.95	0.3
Analytic	98.09	96.73	87.63
Authentic	11.39	15.91	28.9

A comparative analysis of linguistic patterns in Dawn and The Express Tribune articles, juxtaposed against the average for formal language, unveils distinctive trends in their use of Definitive LIWC dimensions. In terms of I-words (I, me, my), Dawn employs these sparingly at 0.06%, while The Express Tribune registers virtually none at 0%, both falling below the average for formal language, which stands at 0.67%. Notably, The Express Tribune displays a more reserved use of first-person pronouns. Regarding the presentation of sentiment, Dawn shows a positive tone at 1.16%, while The Express Tribune follows closely at 0.3%, both notably lower than the formal language average of 2.33%. However, the use of a negative tone is more apparent in The Express Tribune (3.77%) compared to Dawn (1.88%), surpassing the formal language average of 1.38%. In the realm of social discourse, both print media outlets surpass the average for formal language (6.54%), with Dawn using social words at 11.23% and The Express Tribune at 10.15%. However, Dawn displays a higher prevalence of social words.

Cognitive processes are employed less often in both publications compared to the formal language average of 7.95%, with Dawn at 5.5% and The Express Tribune at 5.45%. Both publications exhibit an equivalent level of cognitive engagement.

Examining measurements of allure and moralization, Dawn presents allure at 2.7% and moralization at 0.99%, both lower than the respective formal language averages of 3.58% and 0.3%. Similarly, The Express Tribune's allure (2.35%) and moralization (1.95%) fall below the formal language averages. The analysis of summary variables reveals a consistent trend across both publications, with a notably higher analytical dimension. Dawn's analytical dimension is at 98.09%, and The Express Tribune closely follows at 96.73%, both surpassing the formal language average of 87.63%. Conversely, both publications exhibit a lower prevalence of authenticity, with Dawn at 11.39% and The Express Tribune at 15.91%, compared to the formal language average of 28.9%.

Comparison of Variables' Summeries

In summary, while both Dawn and The Express Tribune share similarities in their analytical approaches, they exhibit nuanced differences in their use of linguistic dimensions, contributing to a distinctive stylistic profile in each publication.

Comparison of variables' summaries reveals a compendium of variables which have been analyzed, making it oblivious that Dawn and Express Tribune have cast the immoderate analytics which is beyond the formal average score of language at LIWC. Dichotomously, both newspapers have cast the below-average authentic score at LIWC. This points out the questions in their representation of one of the most delicate issues of society. This would not only drive the laymen but also drive the expert opinion concerning the issue. For example, without considering the public perception, cultural context, sensitivity of language, audience perspective and societal facets which

may have cast a harsher impact on readers and outsiders as well Tahir, A.M (2024), additionally findings of respective articles have revealed that Urdu newspaper uses harsher tone and language in the newspaper while representing the CSA. In the same token, this paper also casts similar findings of The Dawn and The Express Tribune's newspapers that both have used high negative tone and deficient positive tone at LIWC software. Another thing which is common between Tahir's article and this article is both suggest that Newspapers whether it is Urdu or English both have used CSA as a product of political agenda setting rather than representing CSA focusing primarily.

Critical Discourse Analysis

As per Dijk's (1998) socio-cognitive model discursive practices have been applied below:

Articles: The Dawn News Paper		Date
1.1	<i>"The incident prompted Sindh Chief Minister Murad Ali Shah to take notice of it after which the Karachi police chief constituted a special committee to investigate the case and bring the perpetrators to justice."</i>	Dawn: 25 Oct 2022
1.2	<i>"Taking notice of the rape, the CM directed the police to arrest the culprits forthwith. He also directed Women Development Minister Shahla Raza to take the entire family into protective care. "This is totally unacceptable and cannot be forgiven. I want the culprits behind bars immediately," he told Karachi police chief Javed Odho over the phone. The CM was informed that a police team had been formed to arrest the culprits. The chief minister directed the city police chief to check the CCTV footage, identify suspects' vehicle and arrest them. The CM was informed that the family was kept at a women police station under protective care."</i>	Dawn: 25 Oct 2022
1.3	<i>"Minister Shela Raza said the whole society is paralyzed due to such "savage beasts" and parents should also not leave their children at the mercy of such people and take care of them."</i>	Dawn: 26 Oct 2022
1.4	<i>"The incident had earned the Sindh government strong criticism on the social media, forcing Sindh Chief Minister Syed Murad Ali Shah to take notice of it and order arrest of culprits."</i>	Dawn: 28 Oct 2022
1.5	<i>"According to the contents of the FIR, the victim's father had already passed away and her mother lived on a footpath near the shrine of Abdullah Shah Ghazi in Clifton. Narrating the ordeal, she told the police that on Sunday, at around 11:12am, her daughter went to a Clifton shopping mall for begging. She said her daughter on her return told her that two men forcibly took her to an unknown place in their car and subjected her to criminal assault, added the police."</i>	Dawn: 28 Oct 2022

1.1 Pragmatical

These lines highlight the gravity of the offence has prompted CM to take serious notice against the offender who has committed the offence of child sexual abuse. Moreover, the Police Chief followed the order of Chief Minister Sindh Syed Murad Ali Shah. In turn, the CM may get such prompts more than 12 times a day because "Sahil's NGO report affirms that the occurrence of child sexual abuse is 12 or more than 12 cases in a day". Moreover, several cases also went unreported due to cultural barriers and societal prejudice. Thus, CM may get like prompts in every two hours because the case of child sexual abuse is reported and the police chief may recurrently forms and dismantles a special investigation team in every two hours. Due to CSA's cases are reported to be solved within 72 hours of the period in case study. Which probably raise question. Like, Does all CSA cases are being solved within 72 hours of time frame? Obviously, it is not possible to solve the case in 72 hours. This case was not especial because the child was molested. This case merely solved

because CM got prompted and media found allure case study. Or, there might be some other factors that trigger both to the CM and to the media to take serious notice. It can be political agenda setting or having time to cash the media's ratings (TRP) through such delicate cases.

Similarly, the media has its agenda, with political issues taking priority. Stories related to child abuse often did not appear on the front pages of newspapers until they gained attention on social media or mainstream media (Habib et al., 2023; Tahir, A.M, 2024). Other than that, media outlets are not doing their work proficiently to make such prompts on all cases, but they feel what cases need to be highlighted to make newsworthiness. This is how the media gain a reputable image in front of leader but lose their value on the professionalism index globally.

1.2 Pragmatical

This piece of news article is filled with the most authoritative people and influential dignitaries of the country. Consequently, it is easily

predictable tactics of the author in this appendix and how they make the news sensationalise throughout the country by using celebrities or government dignitaries to gain the attention of readers. This is how an appeal to authority fallacy works. The motive of the media was not child sexual abuse as a primary concern, but they had the motive of tabloidization for the meaningless crime story which would prove beneficial to generate profit. Unfortunately, the media remains, just to cover sponsorship and aid as well as rather than educate the public socially, psychologically and emotionally but they are driving laymen towards isolation and powerlessness. Correspondingly, they also form novel definitions of society, what is acceptable and what is not. There are no established ethical guidelines for publishing or framing stories about child sexual abuse (Habib et al., 2023). They only have negative frames rather than positive things to do so.

1.2 Semantical

It has been reported that “CM had ordered the police to check the CCTV footage”. It demonstrates that police and their teams had not so far realized that it is important work to go through the surveillance, but CM was more insightful than our police to direct them to do what they are unable to do. This is disappointing how the media again goes out of context by showing influence to create “nominal pseudo authorities” to manipulate or coax the public towards a particular story rather than giving complete coverage to the case till justice is served.

1.3 Grammatical

The aforesaid word “savage beast” is composed of adjective (savage) and noun (beast) savage refers to wild, uncultivated, abnormal and uncivilized human beings. This word reflects the grudge against the offender but what difference does it make when the state's fourth pillar projects a predatory image of the offender? On the other side, journalists talk about the types of sexual offenders who have been suffering psychological disorders like paedophilia who prone to sexually attract young children. Even the law does not allow anybody to make someone to derogate

someone else so does ethics, but the media is free to go with such hotlines. This is out of the Modern Penology's principle which proposes that the sex offender might have some psychological disorder. Therefore, they are possible to be ameliorated with cognitive behavioural therapy uttering such words make that principle harder to implement within the Pakistan context.

1.3 Criminological Perspective

This elucidates media-produced behaviour throughout “criminological definitions”. While some theories suggest that criminal behaviour is learned behaviour one who commits such deeds should not be discouraged by revealing their anonymity but must incapacitate them and make them a normal person who should be complying with the normative applications of society by treating such criminals under the criminal justice system? Accordingly, that is also the perspective of sociologists, e.g., Edwin Sutherland and Travis Hirshi. This is meant by the criminal justice system. Thus, criminals should be treated in rehabilitation centres to not commit and repeat such crimes again. Therefore, the media outlets are liable to play a crucial role by suggesting the reintegration of criminals rather than disintegration by portraying derogatory images of those offenders. Once an offense is committed, it will never be reversed, but we have a second opportunity to rehabilitate them, which should not be overlooked.

1.4 Semantical

The aforesaid text is used to show that the government had faced strong criticism over social media therefore Sindh's Chief Minister Murad Ali Shah took serious notice.

1.4 Pragmatical

In light of the situation mentioned in quotation 1.4, it appears that the CM's actions were not prompted but compelled by circumstances. This argument raises questions against the approach of the government. I would say if the governments solving such problems in this way i.e., why they do not restore the committee which was banned in 2021 Anti-Rape Committee consists of 26 members? Let the problem be resolved by the committee. Thus, once renowned philosopher

Plato said if all people do their jobs rightly and don't interfere with another person job then society will run smoothly and progressively.

1.5 Pragmatical

The above-listed information might be considered unauthentic or unable to prove something because the police are not the single person who has said it (not specifying exact source). Accordingly, in this paragraph, an emotional picture is used for persuasiveness. For example, she has no one who will take care of the abused child. Secondly, she lives on the footpath. Thirdly, her father had already passed away; fourthly, she was a beggar; and fifthly, she was raped forcefully, which was not, but it was lured rape for incentives. All the tactics are used to make an emotional picture to draw the attention of the reader. If she is a beggar and her father passes away, this sort of things concludes for example another girl whose father belongs to a middle-class family will be denied justice. Thus, these sorts of words create limitations for readers so that they will raise their voices against only those cases whose father has died and who have poor family belongings. It is a fact that a sizable amount of rape occurs in poor and low socioeconomic classes, and poor working class near urban cities and rural areas (Sahil, 2023; Habib et al., 2023; Tahir, A.M, 2024; Veenema et al., 2015), Moreover, 11-13 and 13-15 age of

victims are largely susceptible and therefore it is a common trend observed in two Pakistani studies from the respective mentioned studies. Even though child sexual abuse is a universally vulnerable incident in which a child might suffer from many mental illnesses, such as post-traumatic stress disorder, obsessive-compulsive personality disorder, and paranoia personality disorder, or morbidity can also be found in them. And can significantly impact a child's wellbeing and require substantial support and care, regardless of their background or family circumstances.

1.5 Semantical

The media's above-mentioned words, such as "Victim's father already passed away, they live on footpath, and they are beggars, and forcibly," such words are used to show that the victims are damaged, which evokes emotional attachment among all rather than dealing with the case practically. Therefore, people demand that swift and uncertain action be taken against the perpetrator to get justice for the victim. If the public consumes such materials, there will be a possibility of incitation amidst poor class and upper-class ideology due to covert manipulation. Those words do not only affect the emotional state of the mind of consumers but also create an us versus them mentality, which is perilous and jeopardises the equilibrium of societal norms.

Articles: The Express Tribune News Paper	Date
<p>2.1 "According to details, On Sunday, at around 11am, two unidentified suspects forcibly took the 10-year-old girl into their car and subjected her to gang rape. Later, the suspects left the girl in the area from where they had picked her at around 2:30 pm."</p> <p>"After the medical examination, a police surgeon confirmed that the girl had been sexually assaulted."</p> <p>"Sindh Chief Minister Syed Murad Ali took strict notice of the incident of rape of the 10-year-old girl and directed the police officials to arrest the accused immediately."</p>	Express Tribune 25 Oct 2022
<p>2.2 "She said that the body of the girl bore violence marks and severe torture. The examination at the hospital also revealed that the girl was gang-raped while samples have been obtained from the girl for DNA and other tests."</p>	Express Tribune 25 Oct 2022
<p>2.3 "The heartless incident took place on Sunday morning when the 10-year-old orphan girl was abducted by the two beastly perverts from Clifton Block 4 within the jurisdiction of Boat Basin police station who took her to a location and allegedly subjected her to gang-rape."</p> <p>"However despite the passage of two days, police are still clueless where the victim had been taken to by her tormentors after abducting her from Clifton Block 4."</p>	Express Tribune 26 Oct 2022
<p>2.4 "He called up his friend Khalid and both sexual predators set off in search of their "prey"."</p>	Express Tribune 27 Oct 2022
<p>2.4 "Soon after the registration of the case, an investigation team was formed under the DIG South's leadership to trace the sexual perverts. 'The investigation team not only solved the blind case within 72 hours but also arrested the two accused,' he added."</p>	Express Tribune 27 Oct 2022
<p>2.4 "The victim belongs to a poor family which had shifted from rural Sindh after the recent floods and was temporarily living near the shrine of Abdullah Shah Ghazi."</p>	Express Tribune 27 Oct 2022
<p>2.4 "Suspects confess to abusing girl in moving car for 40 minutes."</p>	Express Tribune 27 Oct 2022
<p>2.4 "They identified the Suzuki Alto car used in the crime and traced it to a person in Ghotki district who had sold it to a resident of Karachi a few days ago. AIG Qdho said that the new owner of the car was taken into custody, who told police investigators that he had hired a driver, named Ghulam Rasool, to drive his car as online taxi. Even on the day of their arrest they are on search of their prey."</p>	Express Tribune 27 Oct 2022

2.1 Pragmatical

This news article detailing the abduction and gang rape of a 10-year-old girl. The incident transpired on a Sunday at approximately 11 am, with the perpetrators abandoning the girl in the same vicinity from which she was taken around 2:30 pm. Subsequently, the girl's mother sought medical attention for her at Jinnah Hospital, where a thorough examination confirmed the sexual assault. Dr. Samia, the police surgeon, attested to the severe torture and violent marks evident on the girl's body. This abhorrent transgression represents a blatant breach of the law and a profound injustice to the victim. It is imperative for the authorities to promptly apprehend the perpetrators, ensuring the swift administration of justice and the safeguarding of all citizens, particularly vulnerable children.

2.2 Semantical

News article's report that the 10-year-old girl who was abducted and gang-raped bore violent marks and suffered severe torture. The medical examination conducted at Jinnah Hospital confirmed the sexual assault, and the police surgeon Dr. Samia who has attested to the severity of the girl's injuries. The use of the term "bore violence marks" indicates that the girl was subjected to physical violence, while the phrase "severe torture" suggests that she was subjected to prolonged and intense suffering. Such acts of violence and cruelty are reprehensible and must be condemned in the strongest possible terms. The authorities must take all necessary measures to ensure that the perpetrators are brought to justice and that the victim receives the necessary care and support to recover from this traumatic experience. It is essential to prioritise the safety and protection of all citizens, particularly vulnerable children, and to work towards creating a society where such heinous acts are not tolerated.

2.3 Semantical

The specific words and phrases employed in the news article to convey their literal meaning. The article employs the term "heartless incident" to describe the abduction and gang rape of the 10-year-old girl, underscoring the cruelty and brutality of the act. The word "abducted" is utilised to describe the forcible taking of the girl, while the phrase "beastly

perverts" is employed to describe the perpetrators of the crime, emphasizing the deviant and unacceptable nature of their behaviour. The article also employs the term "prey" to describe the victim, a term commonly used to describe animals hunted by predators. The use of this term in the context of a human being is dehumanizing and reinforces the notion that the victim was powerless and vulnerable. It is crucial to acknowledge the impact of language in shaping our perceptions and attitudes towards victims of crime and to utilize language that is respectful and dignified.

2.4 Pragmatical

The passage highlights the portrayal of the suspects as sexual predators and underscores the term "sexual predator" as a word that naturally captures the reader's attention. Furthermore, the article characterises the victim as an innocent girl. While the victim's innocence is a crucial aspect of the case, the commentary suggests that the publisher should prioritise presenting information about the case rather than employing emotionally charged language to captivate the audience. This perspective emphasises the importance of maintaining a balanced and objective approach in reporting sensitive and distressing events, ensuring that the focus remains on the facts and the pursuit of justice, rather than sensationalizing the narrative.

2.4 Pragmatical

The passage underscores the publisher's emphasis on promoting the Karachi police department by highlighting the resolution of the case within 72 hours. It suggests the necessity for the publisher to offer accurate and appropriate information that aligns with the audience's expectations. The author observes that a previous publication depicted the police as being without leads, prompting skepticism regarding the sudden claim of solving the case within 72 hours. The author raises the question of whether the police had miraculously acquired the means to swiftly resolve the case. This perspective underscores the significance of providing factual and transparent information to the public, particularly in cases involving sensitive and distressing events.

2.4 Pragmatical

The passage seems to be attempting to evoke sympathy from the audience, although it is unnecessary to disclose the girl's socioeconomic status. The primary obligation is to pursue justice for her as a human being, and it appears that the audience's attention is being exploited for commercial gain. The fundamental question raised here pertains to the reasons behind the active involvement of the police department and the Chief Minister of Sindh, as well as the commendation of their actions as heroic. This prompts further inquiry into why this particular case has garnered such pronounced attention, particularly given the numerous critical cases that arise daily.

2.4 Pragmatical

The passage underscores a disparity in the reported duration of the incident. It indicates that, as per a specific publication, the entire sequence of events lasted 40 minutes. However, another publication from October reports that the girl was abducted at 11 am and dropped off at 2:30 pm at the same location, suggesting a duration of 3 hours and 30 minutes. This inconsistency raises questions regarding the precision of the initial report and necessitates further investigation into the actual timeline of the events.

2.4 Pragmatical

The passage raises concerns regarding the efficacy of the police department in promptly resolving the case within 72 hours. It emphasises the apparent inconsistency between the initial assertion of the police being uninformed and their subsequent capacity to conduct interviews on the same night and apprehend suspects the following morning with the aid of CCTV footage. Additionally, it expresses doubt regarding the sudden effectiveness of the Karachi police, especially considering their ability to track a suspect from Tando-Allahyar and gather details about a car from Ghotki.

2.4 Pragmatical

The passage underscores the exceptional character of the situation as described by the police. It raises doubts about the veracity of the police's assertion that the suspects were in

pursuit of another target. Furthermore, the passage highlights that the police had already taken the suspects into custody, and one of them had even admitted to the crime on the day of his arrest. The passage implies that the police's claim of searching for another target may lack a factual basis or be misleading.

Limitation and Future Direction

This paper relies on only two newspaper samples, which restricts the generalizability of the findings.

Moreover, All the other regional and international perspective are unexplored which may bring rigour in generalizability of the findings in the context of the Pakistani media. In addition to that, multiple case studies will bring more robust findings in The CSA's context in the Pakistani print media.

Language barrier is also acknowledge such stream will also cover regional and national perspective as well.

Inclusion of more enlarge sample of newspapers and numbers of CSA cases would bring more generalizable findings.

On the top that, conducting separate study on qualitative and quantitative would also bring different results that could be generalize and may expose new techniques that might have been overlooked author of this research.

CONCLUSION

This research addresses the case of Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) to scrutinize how it is portrayed in Pakistani news media. This study determines whether the media chooses sensationalism over righteousness or justice. The results exposed some common methods of media coverage, when it comes to such news writings quotes from authoritative figures are often used and interwoven into the text including statements by Chief Ministers or police officials. These quotations boost credibility and newsworthiness. But it just stirred up more doubt as to the motivation of media, devoting attention not so much to complete coverage but rather sensationalism. Furthermore, this research revealed that some articles also employ emotional and sympathetic language to affect readers on an emotionally. Although it would focus attention on the problem, it could distort public opinion and create one-sided stories. Furthermore, this

controversial topic itself indicates the importance of responsible journalism, journalists mustn't mislead readers or take advantage of them economically. After all, this study concludes that portrayal of Child Sexual Abuse in Pakistani news media is influenced by various factors such as social taboos, media agendas and cultural norms. The study's implications extend to professionals and students operating in media education, academia, politics and research. These conclusions contribute a minor but crucial step toward the concept of social.

However, the print media outlets specifically The Dawn News and The Express Tribune use high above score analytical words with low authenticity. This tactics permeates that print media outlets uses authoritative figures to gain readership. Furthermore, they use modern tactics such as theories are used to describe that how sources are being hidden and the cases are being rationalized that why only the few cases in representation of CSA are selected. Thereby, it will not be absurd to acknowledge that their primary motive of representation of the CSA as a merely case study, in which profit is made beside political campaign is done.

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